

OF WORK ON TEXT ANALYSIS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article provides information about text analysis in primary education, the formation of skills in teaching primary school students to express their opinions, and the development of students' oral speech.

Keywords: text, analysis, comprehension, oral speech, native language reading literacy, literary text, comprehension, thought, reading.

The process of understanding the text seems to be a process of active processing, an active selection of important components that make it an internal component of the extended text. There are many other definitions of understanding: “ Understanding is the process of understanding the internal connections in the text ” , “ Understanding is an action towards knowledge, the production of knowledge in the process of receiving the text ” , etc. Summarizing the diversity of definitions, it is clear that the category of understanding is inextricably linked with the understanding of “ meaning ” : meaning is the most important component of the essence of understanding [5; 328-b].

This perspective is becoming increasingly relevant in modern society, where there is an increasing emphasis on students' ability to use the information they learn from reading. The focus is shifting from demonstrating understanding to demonstrating how to apply the acquired information to new projects and situations.

In the analysis of texts in primary education, special attention should be paid to the aesthetic value and artistic beauty of the text being studied, and at the same time, the artistic literacy of students should be ensured. It is desirable that native language and reading literacy lessons should help students to distinguish between literary texts, determine the artistic means through which life events are reflected and what images are created, and develop the skills to analyze the text as a whole. As students master the text and analyze what they have read, they also understand its content and the importance of its leading ideas.

“The formation of personality traits in primary school students is quite different from that in middle and upper grades,” emphasizes Q. Husanboyeva, author of the textbook “Methodology of Teaching Literature in Primary Education.” “A child of this age has little life experience and does not know how to draw conclusions. He imitates more. It is advisable that the educational and upbringing process carried out in primary schools should be focused on expressing opinions and reactions, not on drawing conclusions, in accordance with the age and intellectual capabilities of children. For this reason, the task of a primary school teacher is to be able to correctly pose the issue in the lesson, to interest the student, and to disturb his feelings” [7; 36-b].

In primary education, the skill of teaching students to express their opinions begins with the creation of a simple sentence, then proceeds through the stages of reacting to a picture or text, and then creating a small text. At such times, the teacher's activity, approach, and the extent to which he can use innovative methods and techniques are of great importance.

T. Yusupova points out that in the process of working on the text and preparing to create the text, students must acquire the following knowledge, skills and competencies based on the requirements of state educational standards:

- understand the main idea expressed in the studied text;
- be able to draw logical conclusions from independently read texts;

- determine the type, language, and style of a text that has been studied or created independently;
- distinguish between essay texts and structure them correctly;
- selecting and appropriately using language tools that shape the content of the text, its stylistic aspects, and connect sentences;
- be able to make a sentence with stylistic flaws concise and perfect;
- be able to effectively use word combinations, phrases and figurative expressions, proverbs and wise sayings in the process of creating a text;
- be able to create short texts on a given topic in scientific, artistic, journalistic, official, and colloquial styles;
- be able to edit and analyze a ready-made text (given or created in language classes);
- be able to write short reviews, recommendations, and suggestions that reflect the content of the text;
- classify electronic didactic slides and communicative tables in a scientific, scientific-artistic style and use them to compose scientific texts on the topic;
- acquire cultural communication skills and know how to create texts on this topic in different styles;
- write reviews and abstracts of articles published in newspapers and magazines, freely use dictionaries and linguistic dictionaries;
- creating a new text based on a ready-made text [6; 78-b].

Sh. Abduraimov's article "Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of Assessing Reading Comprehension Skills in Native Language Education," the reading comprehension process is studied in four levels:

Understanding word-level information – recognize graphemes and graphic images, read drawings and diagrams, translate them into meaning, understand the original and figurative meanings of words, and understand the function and meaning of grammatical forms.

Understanding sentence-level information – understanding the function and content of sentences and phrases in the text, and understanding explicit and implicit information.

Understanding text-level information – understanding paragraphs and the general content of the text, understanding the grammatical structure of the text, integrating information in the text, perceiving main and additional information in the text, dividing the text into meaningful blocks.

Comprehension – understanding the idea of the text, evaluating the author's point of view, and being able to apply the information in the text to a real-life situation [1; 25-b].

emphasizes that in the formation of reading skills in native language and literature classes in secondary schools, attention should be paid to exercises and tasks in the following areas:

- be able to read texts fluently and evaluate self-reading from the point of view of literacy;
- learn and apply various strategies for developing reading comprehension skills through the use of different reading methods;
- select appropriate learning materials for different purposes;
- be able to search for information from various sources.
- be able to recommend interesting educational material in order to form a positive attitude towards learning;
- focus on different methods of developing reading comprehension skills (e.g., skimming, word-for-word reading, deductive reading);
- use reading comprehension strategies (e.g., understanding the content and structure of texts, illustrations and headings - being able to distinguish main information from secondary information, asking generalizing questions);
- evaluate the content of the text and the author's vocabulary;
- sharing personal reading experiences.
- to form a planned strategy and metacognitive skills necessary for developing reading comprehension skills;

- to identify each individual's needs in developing reading skills and to develop skills to assess them;
- provide opportunities to identify the necessary information from texts of various styles and formats, use it, sort information, and interpret it in relation to life situations;
- develop critical literacy;
- use and evaluate information from various sources;
- to increase interest in different forms and styles of text and to be able to share their acquired reading literacy skills [3; 8-b].

Working on a text requires reading and understanding it holistically. Teaching students to work on a literary text involves educating them through the formation and development of their literary and aesthetic analysis skills. Analyzing the text of a work helps young students understand the author's thoughts, feelings, and conclusions, and awakens their independent attitude to the events expressed in the work. Analysis of a work requires the teacher to direct the students' activities towards a specific goal. The student becomes familiar with the content of the work while reading it. While reading enriches the senses and develops the mind, analysis helps to deeply understand the meaning behind the work.

Sh. Abduraimov, summarizing existing theoretical views, believes that it is appropriate to base the assessment of reading comprehension skills in native language education on the following indicators - constructs:

- be able to find and understand information clearly expressed in the text;
- understanding the meaning of lexical units in the text;
- understand the meaning and function of grammatical units in the text;
- understanding the grammatical structure of the text;
- understanding information expressed explicitly in the text;
- understanding hidden information in the text;
- read visual information provided in drawings and diagrams in the text;
- understanding the connections between verbal and visual information in the text;

- understanding the semantic connections in the text;
- understanding the general meaning of parts of the text;
- divide the text into meaningful blocks;
- identify the author's purpose in the text;
- understanding the idea of the text;
- understand and interpret the content of the text;
- be able to evaluate the clarity of ideas and the author's point of view in the text;
- to some extent integrate the student's prior knowledge and information from the text;
- be able to apply the knowledge and concepts learned from the text in practice.

According to the author, these stages do not occur in all readers of a text. That is why we witness the different understanding of a particular text by readers who read the same text. This may depend on its physiological and psychological aspects, that is, its receptive capacity or its psycho-psychic or physical state. There are also other factors that affect the reading and understanding of a text [1; 26-b].

Russian scholars also have their own experiences and views on this issue, and M.R.L.ov distinguishes three main ideas about the complex learning process:

1. Perception of words in the text. Being able to read is, first of all, the ability to read by guessing the words they know, used in their daily lives. Reading begins only when the reader can say or remember a specific word that corresponds to a combination of these letters, looking at the letters.

In the process of perceiving these letters as symbols of a particular word, not only vision, but also a person's memory, imagination and consciousness are of great

importance. When reading words, we first teach them not only to memorize the letters, but also to explain what words can be formed from these letters, so that they can be retained in the mind and memory of the reader.

2. Understanding the process associated with the given words in the text. Each word we read can cause some changes in our consciousness, which determines our understanding of this word. In some cases, it creates certain, high-level images in our consciousness, some kind of feeling, desire, or abstract logical process can simply repeat the perceived word or another word associated with it by making it possible.

3. Reading assessment. As we know, the ability not only to read a book, but also to critically evaluate its content is not always observed [4; 203-b].

Understanding, according to A.A. Brudny, is the connecting node between knowledge and communication. The truth of knowledge, the correctness of understanding, is established in practical activity as its correspondence to reality. Since practice is social in nature, this allows us to conclude that the object of knowledge is simultaneously an object of communication [2; 94-b].

Therefore, when analyzing texts given in the textbook of native language and reading literacy for 1st graders, attention is paid mainly to their title, content, correct and expressive reading. After reading the text, questions are asked by the teacher. Therefore, we will consider an example of forming students' dialogue based on the text "Ko`zichok".

Last year, my father bought a lamb from the market for two coins. I took good care of it. I fed it, I grazed it in the meadow. Now, a year later, my lamb has become a ram. We sold it at the market for ten coins. Look, I made eight coins in cash!

The teacher reads the text once, slowly and expressively. Then questions are asked about the text. After that, the students who have listened to the text begin to answer the questions.

The teacher draws the students' attention to the parts of the text, noting that they answer each question correctly. They are warned that in order to find the correct answer to the questions, it is necessary to clearly state the event in the text.

As a result, the team will answer the following questions from the text:

1. What did we buy at the market?
2. How was the lamb cared for?
3. How much did it sell for?

Also, along with reading the text correctly and formulating questions, the oral speech of elementary school students is developed.

The text is a component of the communicative situation and at the same time a product of verbal and mental activity, formed as a result of knowledge of the surrounding reality. Taking this into account, it can be recognized that understanding the text is subject to the same general laws as other types of cognitive activity.

In general, the purpose of perceiving a text for the recipient is to reveal objects and phenomena of reality and establish connections and relationships between them, that is, it is measured by making a transition from the text to the reality behind its content. This process can be considered a special type of assimilation, organization and use of knowledge.

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